

Input Based Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) in Inland Aquaculture of Bankura District, West Bengal

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The adaptation of indigenous technologies has resulted in the development of sustainable and ecologically benign aquaculture practices in many countries of the world. Practice of such knowledge has a long genesis in aquaculture particularly in the South and South-East Asia. ITKs have established itself in the traditional pond-based aquaculture as an integral part of management; either in system designing or as inputs through the years. Though in many cases, these knowledges are not yet validated, they helped the farmers to increase production in many ways. The present paper documented the rich heritage of application of ITKs by the fresh water fish farmers of Bankura district, West Bengal. Bankura district was purposively selected for the present study as freshwater aquaculture practice is highly popular and diverse in this district of West Bengal; also emerged as major carp seed hub in the country. This district is bestowed with different herbs in rain forest, also consists of red soil, alluvial soil and laterite soil, that contributes a lot in developing Indigenous Technical Knowledge. Practice of total 15 ITKs are recorded during the present study. Among them 20% of are recent ITKs, adapted within 10 years, whereas, 53% are being practiced for more than 20 years. Farmers are adaptive in nature and as they are getting positive results, their perception is good about the ITKs. Farmers innovations help them to mitigate their environmental problems in farming management of their own convenient way with these ITKs.

Keywords: Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK), Aquaculture, Seed production, Environmental management, Health management.